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Almaty, Kazakhstan*ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2047-2748>**Abstract**

The article addresses the issue of developing bachelor students' readiness for professional activity from a historical and cultural perspective. It analyzes the historical prerequisites for the formation of professional training and the role of cultural traditions in shaping professional values, worldview, and professional identity of future specialists. Particular attention is given to the influence of historical experience, national culture, and the cultural and educational environment on the process of students' professional development.

It is demonstrated that engagement with historical and cultural heritage contributes to the development of professional thinking, the formation of value orientations, and the improvement of the quality of bachelor-level professional training. The necessity of integrating historical and cultural aspects into the educational process is substantiated as an essential condition for fostering the professional readiness of future specialists.

Keywords: professional readiness, bachelor students, professional activity, historical and cultural approach, higher education, cultural values, professional training, educational process.

Introduction

The vocal mastery of a music teacher has its own specificity, determined by the goals, objectives, and functions of professional vocal activity. The set of specialized knowledge, skills, and competencies required to enhance the vocal mastery of a music teacher, as well as for effective work, self-monitoring, and self-correction of vocal performance, should include historical, theoretical, methodological, vocal-speech, and psychological components.

In higher education practice, both individual and group independent work in vocal training are distinguished. These include working with musical notation, educational and scientific literature, preparation for classes, implementation of vocal performance projects, writing essays, developing individual assignments and collective vocal performance projects, as well as creative tasks, among others [1, p. 59].

The main academic discipline responsible for the formation of vocal mastery among bachelor's students of the educational program "6B01402 – Music Education" is the course "Vocal Studies," which has its own specificity determined by pedagogical objectives. However, an analysis of the curriculum of the discipline "Vocal Studies" suggests that training in solo singing classes is primarily focused on performance activities. The vocal training of bachelor's students is largely based on methods of vocal education designed for professional performers, adapted for use in pedagogical universities.

Modern research has identified the causes of this issue: an insufficient level of historical-theoretical, methodological, and practical preparedness of special-

ists for professional vocal and vocal-pedagogical activity. Therefore, alongside vocal development, the formation of vocal mastery in music teachers must also include historical, theoretical, and methodological training in vocal pedagogy [2].

As is well known, music pedagogy has deep historical traditions and represents a dynamically developing field of knowledge. The historical context allows us to understand the complexities and challenges of the "difficult historical path" of professional vocal training, as well as to incorporate into this training the forms and methods accumulated over centuries of musical art development.

At the present stage of development of Kazakh musical art and creativity, special attention is given to the issue of professional vocal schools. This is обусловлено тем, что in many cases, especially at the initial level (children's music schools, studios, etc.), solo singing is taught by instructors from other areas of specialization (choirmasters, conductors, piano teachers, etc.), who assume that any specialist with a musical education can develop a voice and teach singing. As a result, beginner vocalists often exhibit various vocal deficiencies, such as tension, hoarseness, or nasal tone, which are difficult—and sometimes impossible—to correct later (at the college or university level). Consequently, the true purpose of the professional vocal school, whose experience has been passed down and enriched over centuries, is diminished, and the competency-based approach to vocal training is pushed into the background [3].

Moreover, a review of the scientific literature has shown that, despite the increased attention and sus-

tained interest of scholars in the problem of the formation and development of the national vocal school, information about the genesis and specificity of this phenomenon is most often limited to fragmentary references, mentioned incidentally alongside other studied phenomena of musical art, or reduced to descriptions of the creative portraits of well-known vocalists. Taking these circumstances into account, it is important to study and highlight the specific features of the formation of the professional and pedagogical Kazakh vocal school. Such research makes it possible to systematize and unify the heritage of the past, thereby helping to prevent errors related to professional vocal education in Kazakhstan at the present stage [1–10].

Within the framework of the historical and cultural approach, various cultural-dynamic and historical trends in the evolution of the vocal art of a particular people are examined. Analyzing the scientific works of researchers, it can be noted that, at the level of general scientific understanding, traditional song and vocal creativity is considered a phenomenon of the cultural code of the Kazakh people. This assertion is supported by the fact that the fundamental cause of the disappearance of any ethnic group is not the loss of language or territory, but rather the complete loss of its national musical culture, including song and vocal traditions. It is also important that, while influencing the cultural code of a particular people, song and vocal creativity itself develops under the significant influence of the cultural paradigm established within society [6].

Historically, the origins of the formation and development of the cultural code of the Kazakh people are rooted in the cultural enclave of nomadic civilization, the chronological framework of which encompasses three major historical periods:

1. the conceptual period (8th century BCE – 5th century CE), characterized by the syncretization of cultural enclaves of nomadic and sedentary civilizations, as well as Tengrian and Scythian-Saka traditions;
2. the functional period (6th–14th centuries), marked by the objectification of Turkic and Mongolian civilizations;
3. the transformative period (15th–18th centuries), characterized by the hybridization of the cultural elements of the conceptual and functional periods into what became the Kazakh civilization [7].

The cultural enclave of nomadic civilizations is reflected in the diversity of folklore genres:

1. ritual genres (life-cycle songs, ritual-sacred, and calendar songs), and
2. everyday genres (children's, youth, and folklyrical songs).

In general, the characteristic features of Kazakh folk singing include syncretic solo performance, orality and improvisation, distinctive cantilena style, vitality, and a strong orientation toward the audience. All of these elements express the integrity and richness of Kazakh traditional song culture [8].

At the same time, within the creative heritage of the Kazakh people, specific “specializations” of song traditions can be distinguished depending on the localization of professional performing and compositional schools. These include the Arka, Western, and Zhetysu

singing schools. The Arka and Zhetysu singing schools were formed on the basis of poetic traditions, whereas the Western singing traditions developed primarily from vocal performance practice. The distinctive features of these schools were manifested in their compositional imagery, musical expression, vocal production techniques, and performance manner. Each performer, according to their vocal abilities, adhered to a predefined style of singing characteristic of the particular performing school they represented. The formation of professional singing schools subsequently became the vocal-pedagogical foundation for the development of the national vocal school of Kazakhstan [8].

The vocal-pedagogical approach reflects research directly related to the functioning of national vocal schools and the evaluation of the performance activities of talented vocalists. Based on the results of scientific studies in which the functioning of national vocal-performance schools is considered ambivalently (both as part of national culture and as a professional vocal-pedagogical system), the stages of development of Kazakhstan's vocal school are analyzed through two key factors: external and internal [9].

The external factor includes economic conditions and social realities that determine innovative artistic trends. Internal factors are grounded in continuity and musical traditions, through which, over many centuries, specific concepts of vocal performance were formed in accordance with aesthetic ideals of vocal sound quality; performance techniques and styles were enriched; and the fundamental principles of professional vocal training were established and passed down from generation to generation. Internal factors also directly include the creative activity of representatives of vocal art within the republic [10].

Methodology and Research Methods

The study is based on a systematic approach, which ensures a comprehensive understanding of the development of vocal art; a historical approach, which made it possible to identify the stages of the formation of the vocal school; and a cultural approach, which interprets the process of the formation of the vocal school in Kazakhstan in unity with the processes of historical and cultural enrichment, thereby contributing to the identification of the specific features of the Kazakh vocal school.

The following research methods were employed: content analysis of scientific works, systematization and generalization of archival documents, as well as a retro-analysis of the specific features, divergences, and issues characteristic of different periods in the formation of the vocal school in Kazakhstan.

Research Results and Discussion

The table presents the chronological framework of the stages in the development of vocal art in Kazakhstan. The criteria for chronological systematization include the cultural paradigm, the dominant vocal-pedagogical system of instruction, and changes in vocal performance within the context of intercultural interaction. The uneven development of vocal art in the territory of modern Kazakhstan has led to a lack of precision in chronological boundaries and to their overlapping.

Chronological systematization of the stages in the development of vocal art in Kazakhstan

Cultural Paradigm	Vocal Art	Dominant Vocal-Pedagogical System of Instruction
Tengrian type of culture (7th century BCE – 7th century CE)	Unified genre system; syncretic sacred-ritual singing with sound imitation, timbral layering, meditative character.	Collective oral transmission; unsystematic, non-personalized; traditions passed across generations.
Arab-Islamic culture (7th century CE – 18th century)	Diverse genres with religious and philosophical context; improvisational; preserves earlier traditions	Oral teacher-to-student system; based on imitation and memory; linked with family traditions.
Russian and European cultures (1730s – 1917)	Songs become artistic works; secular themes; high level of folk-professional singing.	Mentor-based training; focus on comprehensive creative development
Socialist culture (1917–1991)	Development of written professionalism; polyphony; European genres (opera, jazz, etc.).	Institutional education: music school – college – conservatory.
National culture of Kazakhstan (1991–present)	Modernization and revival of traditional singing in modern formats.	Bologna system; lifelong learning; global integration.

The historical and cultural perspective on the formation of the vocal school of Kazakhstan has demonstrated that traditional song and vocal creativity is regarded as a phenomenon of the cultural code of the Kazakh people, which represents a cultural enclave of both global and local civilizations. The codifying significance of the cultural code of the Kazakh people in song and vocal creativity is reflected in the following forms of performance: ritual-sacred folklore, ritual-everyday folklore, and oral professional traditions. The results of the study confirm that the vocal school of Kazakhstan is based on the traditions of oral folk-professional singing and encompasses the following stages of its development:

1. works of Kazakh folklore and traditional folk singing;
2. the oral compositional school and folk-professional singing;
3. the national compositional school, opera, and academic singing;
4. professional vocal performance and vocal pedagogy.

The ambivalent understanding of the functioning of national vocal schools has led to the identification of two key factors—social reality and continuity—that determine the development of the vocal school of Kazakhstan. The analysis of external factors (changes in cultural paradigms, intercultural interaction, and the dominant vocal-pedagogical system of instruction) made it possible to systematize the stages of the development of vocal art in Kazakhstan. The study of internal factors, based on continuity and the creative activity of prominent representatives of the national compositional school and vocal performance—taking into account significant historical milestones that determined innovative artistic trends—made it possible to reconstruct the evolution of the vocal school of Kazakhstan. This evolution includes four stages: the professionalization of vocal performance, the conceptualization of vocal pedagogy, and the modernization and autonomization of the Kazakh vocal school.

Thus, the complementary combination of the identified approaches made it possible to conduct a comprehensive study of the phenomenon of the vocal school

of Kazakhstan, whose formation and development constitute a long and multifaceted process that cannot be fully examined from a single perspective.

Conclusion

The conducted historical and cultural analysis of the problem of forming bachelor students' readiness for professional activity allows the following conclusions to be drawn.

In the context of modern higher education, particular importance is attached to the integration of historical experience in professional training and the cultural foundations of education, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the content of future professional activity. The formation of professional readiness among bachelor students is a complex and multi-component pedagogical process that has developed historically and reflects the evolution of educational ideas, cultural values, and the social demand for the training of specialists.

The historical and cultural approach demonstrates that conceptions of professional training have evolved from a narrowly specialized orientation toward a holistic development of the future specialist's personality, including professional knowledge, practical skills, value orientations, and cultural competence. This approach makes it possible to consider the professional training of bachelor students as a process of integrating learners into the cultural space of the profession, mastering professional traditions, norms, and values, as well as forming professional identity.

The readiness of bachelor students for professional activity is formed through the interaction of several interrelated components: cognitive (professional knowledge), activity-based (practical skills and abilities), value-motivational (professional attitudes and motivation), and cultural (understanding the cultural context of the profession). At the same time, historical and cultural analysis makes it possible to reveal the significance of professional education traditions, national and cultural characteristics of specialist training, and their influence on the formation of professional competencies of future bachelors.

Thus, the historical and cultural perspective allows the process of forming bachelor students' readiness for

professional activity to be viewed as an integrated system based on the continuity of educational traditions, cultural values, and modern requirements of professional training. The effectiveness of forming such readiness largely depends on the inclusion of cultural values, professional heritage, and modern educational technologies in the educational process, ensuring the connection between theoretical training and practical activity.

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